

Subjective Well-Being and Migration: Policy Recommendations based on the MIGWELL Project

Research Report 4.2

MIGWELL

Well-being and Migration:
The Hungary – Austria Migration Nexus

Dávid Sümeghy, Borbála Göncz, György Lengyel,
Ádám Németh, Zsolt Németh, Lilla Tóth

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Institute for Urban and Regional Research at the Austrian Academy of Sciences

Centre for Empirical Social Research at the Corvinus University of Budapest

Department of Finno-Ugrian Studies, University of Vienna

Scientific Advisory Board:

Department of Sociology, University of Vienna

Hungarian Demographic Research Institute

Hungarian Central Statistical Office

MIGWELL’s website: [LINK](#)

MIGWELL’s outputs will be uploaded to: [LINK](#)

Inquiries can be directed to: Institute for Urban and Regional Research at the Austrian Academy of Sciences, isr@oeaw.ac.at or Centre for Empirical Social Research at the Corvinus University of Budapest, borbala.goncz@uni-corvinus.hu

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MIGWELL at a glance

The MIGWELL project focuses on the nexus of migration and well-being in Hungary and Austria. Using quantitative and qualitative research methods, it seeks to explore the impacts of migration on subjective well-being in the case of Hungarian immigrants in Austria as well as the effects of subjective well-being differences on emigration potential in Hungary. The approach of this project is innovative not only because it links the concepts of ‘well-being’ and ‘migration’, but also because it interprets their two-way causal relationship within one research framework. Since the Covid-19 pandemic might have a profound impact on both pillars, MIGWELL will also reflect on the rapidly changing socio-economic and well-being related issues that have emerged due to the epidemic throughout the life cycle of the project. The theoretical expansion of these concepts and the empirical findings of the project may contribute to more effective policies in both countries.

1. Introduction

Governments, whether for better or worse, play a fundamental role in shaping individual life outcomes and societal trajectories (Layard & De Neve, 2023). As policymakers navigate increasingly complex social, environmental, and economic challenges, there has been growing interest in incorporating findings from happiness and well-being research into policy formulations and governance.

The underlying idea is compelling: if the goal of government is to improve people’s lives, then understanding what actually contributes to well-being should inform public policy (Layard, 2005). However, the translation of well-being science into effective policy remains limited and often fraught with practical, conceptual, and ethical challenges. While earlier resistance may have stemmed from scepticism toward concepts like happiness or quality of life, today the primary barrier lies in the lack of applied knowledge and experience necessary for effective implementation (Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2019). In some cases, even when research findings are available, they fail to penetrate the policy arena due to lack of awareness or outdated assumptions held by decision-makers (Tonon, 2022).

Besides the political arena, the dissemination of well-being research via the media is essential for fostering public understanding and democratic discourse around national priorities (Frey, 2020; Hicks et al., 2013). National statistics offices, for instance, may publish indicators related to quality of life, economic performance, and environmental sustainability, but without integration into public and policy debates, these measures have little transformative power.

Despite some advances, scholars note the limited real-world impact of well-being policies (Hayden & Wilson, 2018), and empirical studies still struggle to provide conclusive evidence that government action leads to sustained improvements in subjective well-being (Duncan, 2010). Worse still, poorly designed interventions may inadvertently reduce well-being, in this way highlighting the risks of misguided policies that lack a robust evidence base.

“I looked at how, for example, immigration affects happiness of receiving populations. And policymakers, would they, for instance be more alarmed if they read research where immigration, for example, increases wages or decreases wages. Versus were we say that immigration increases life satisfaction or decrease life satisfaction of local people. I mean, when would they take results more seriously?”

Expert interview, well-being scholar

At the same time, failing to consider well-being in policymaking may allow economic growth to remain the dominant metric, even when it comes at significant ecological or social costs (Colman, 2022).

2. Aims of the report

The purpose of this document is to support policymakers in making data-driven decisions based on the research findings of the MIGWELL project. Our project focused on the subjective well-being of Hungarians living in Austria as well as the population in Hungary, and identified factors that contribute to a happier and more satisfied life. Presenting these factors is the primary aim of this report. Our main target group in Austria consists of politicians and professionals working in the fields of migration and integration, while in Hungary the entire policymaking community may take interest in our findings, as subjective well-being can be approached and influenced from various angles, ranging from workplaces and family environments to sports and the civil sector. In addition, in the case of Hungary, those factors also deserve special policy attention which are associated with the lower subjective well-being of individuals intending to emigrate. This report is based both on our statistical models created from our own survey data and on interviews conducted with experts and policymakers. By combining these two data sources, we highlight the factors that influence subjective well-being either positively or negatively. Our goal is to provide information that enables politicians to address the negative factors affecting happiness and to broaden access to the factors that contribute to its growth. The report first provides an overview of subjective well-being, its measurability, and its role in policymaking processes. We then present our recommendations for Austria, followed by those intended for Hungary. Finally, we have compiled several proposals that would require joint cooperation between the two countries. We also support these recommendations with studies from the academic literature.

3. Measurement of subjective well-being

Over the last two decades, subjective well-being (SWB) has gained increasing attention from researchers and policymakers alike as a critical complement to traditional objective indicators like GDP, income, and employment. As noted by Diener and colleagues (2009, p. 215), “the planet will be a better place to live when the measures of subjective well-being are put in place, and when they are used by both leaders and ordinary citizens.” Indeed, relying solely on GDP omits key aspects of social and psychological health, and overlooks the long-term dynamics of individual and societal well-being. Stiglitz, Fitoussi and Sen further stress the importance of the measurements in their famous report (2009, p. 9): “what we measure shapes what we collectively strive to pursue - and what we pursue determines what we measure.” In this sense, measuring well-being is not a mere technical activity, but it is a normative, political, and strategic choice.

“You don't know what actually people think or what are the preferences of people? What is their satisfaction with life and with different domains of life? It can be much more effective to understand priorities or what are, let's say the domains for policing which policymakers should address. I mean a subjective outcome may capture, say priorities for people, that maybe the policymakers do not have no idea, how to capture.”

Expert interview, former OECD economist

Subjective well-being is typically broken down into three core dimensions, and we have used the same typology during our research:

- Evaluative well-being: This refers to overall life satisfaction - people’s overall assessment of their lives, and the domains of their lives.
- Hedonic well-being: The presence of positive affect and the absence of negative affect in daily experiences.
- Eudaimonic well-being: A sense of meaning, purpose, and psychological functioning.

The question may arise: “Which SWB metric should we measure, and to guide policy-making?” The answer is that each dimension serves different policy goals. The selection of indicators is both technical and normative. While Andrew Clark and colleagues (2016) suggest that different SWB measures tend to correlate and the choice among them may not drastically alter conclusions, other scholars stress the importance of measurement pluralism, capturing well-being through multiple life domains (Austin, 2018). When aiming to improve life satisfaction, evaluative measures are most useful; for daily experiences, hedonic indicators are relevant; and for policies addressing purpose and meaning in life, eudaimonic metrics provide key insights though they remain the least explored in public policy (Graham & MacLennan, 2020). Best-practice guidance recommends using all three types of measures in national surveys, forming a comprehensive well-being dashboard (Exton & Shinwell, 2018; Graham & MacLennan, 2020;

Hicks et al., 2013). However, if due to time or financial constraints the measurement can focus only one indicator, it should be overall life satisfaction. Daniel Benjamin and colleagues (2014) found that individuals tend to prioritize life satisfaction over other forms of SWB, suggesting it may serve as a “core” indicator.

Ultimately, SWB measures should supplement, not supplant, objective indicators (Helliwell, 2011). A dashboard approach, combining SWB with data on income, health, and employment, provides a fuller picture of societal progress.

A wide variety of tools have been developed to measure SWB, from single-item life satisfaction scales to multi-dimensional survey modules. National Statistics Offices in countries like Austria have implemented regular, comprehensive SWB measurement programs. The “Wie geht’s Österreich?” initiative, inspired by the 2009 Stiglitz Commission, began in 2012 and tracked 30+1 key indicators annually, including life satisfaction (Statistik Austria, 2021). Later, it evolved into the quarterly “So geht’s uns heute” survey, which included affective well-being questions as well, and was followed by the longitudinal “Wie geht’s uns in Österreich?” study tracking 5,000 households. These longitudinal studies are particularly valuable, as they help identify causal relationships between life circumstances and SWB outcomes (Diener et al., 2009; HM Treasury, 2021a). It is also worth mentioning the Migration Survey operated by Statistik Austria, which has been conducted by the institute since 2021 and primarily serves to monitor integration objectives. The representative survey includes ethnic groups from certain countries of origin that are part of the sample every year, alongside others that are included temporarily. The survey also addresses the evaluative aspect of subjective well-being; however, the scale used in the related question differs from the commonly used 0–10 scale, making comparisons more difficult.

“For politicians, it’s a very important handbook [Statistical Yearbook, which contains the results of the Migration Survey], with recent data, and it’s quite important in that field.”

Expert interview, Statistik Austria

In the case of Hungary despite the Central Statistical Office is developing indicators and publishing life satisfaction data (KSH, 2025), it was not included in the OECD's 2018 review of policy uses of well-being metrics (Exton & Shinwell, 2018). A comprehensive survey of subjective well-being was conducted in the 2016 Microcensus, where evaluative, affective, and eudaimonic variables were measured in a dedicated block. Since 2020, the longitudinal monitoring of subjective well-being has been carried out by KINCS (Kopp Mária Intézet a Népesedésért és a Családokért), which examines, on a monthly basis, the Hungarian population’s life satisfaction, happiness, perceived health, and subjective assessment of their personal situation and the state of the country (KINCS, 2024). The data and findings from these

satisfaction surveys also reach policymakers. In February 2024, the Parliamentary Information Service prepared an information sheet for Members of Parliament titled “Happiness and Satisfaction in Life” (Vajda, 2024).

4. Subjective well-being and policy

The idea that policy should promote people's well-being is hardly new. Thomas Jefferson famously asserted in 1809 that “*the care of human life and happiness and not their destruction is the only legitimate object of good government*”. Yet, for most of modern political history, such aspirations were relegated to rhetoric, while actual policymaking focused on more quantifiable outcomes such as GDP growth, employment, or inflation. As a result, many scholars and governments have begun advocating for the integration of subjective well-being into policymaking as both a more holistic and human-centred metric (Diener et al., 2009; Layard & De Neve, 2023). Subjective well-being indicators capture how people experience their lives, offering a nuanced picture of societal health. As the HM Treasury’s *Green Book* highlights, SWB measures provide a unique lens that complements traditional objective indicators and enables policymakers to identify what truly matters to citizens (HM Treasury, 2020; Exton & Shinwell, 2018).

“I’m not involved in strategy-making, but in terms of quality of life – if we can call it that – it is practically part of strategic decision-making.”

Policy-maker interview, ministerial commissioner

The inclusion of SWB in policy is supported by both ethical theory and political philosophy. From the perspective of Amartya Sen’s capabilities approach, well-being is not merely about material wealth or utility but about the real freedoms people possess to live a life they have reason to value (Sen, 1999; Austin, 2018). This aligns closely with the aims of policy that values individuals’ capacity to pursue their own conception of the good life.

Wren-Lewis (2013) draws on Rawlsian theory to argue that some psychological dimensions of well-being, such as positive affect, should be treated as *primary goods*. Legitimate targets of policy not as ends in themselves, but as means to autonomy, health, and civic participation. Layard & De Neve (2023) similarly stress that SWB should become the overarching goal of policy. This does not imply an authoritarian imposition of happiness, but rather a shift in priority: policies should be evaluated by how much well-being they generate, not merely by their monetary returns. This view is echoed by Frey and Stutzer (2010), who caution against technocratic overreach, emphasizing that SWB data should *inform* democratic decision-making, not replace it. As Frey (2020) notes, it would be deeply wrong to impose happiness from above. Rather, happiness research should empower citizens to make better-informed decisions about their own lives.

A growing number of governments (Slovenia is the closest one to our spatial focus) have embraced the well-being approach at an institutional level. For example, the UK’s *Green Book* methodology explicitly outlines how SWB can be integrated into every phase of the policy

cycle, from early research to strategic planning, option appraisal, and evaluation (HM Treasury, 2020; 2021a). Notably, the UK, along with countries such as New Zealand, Iceland, and Finland, are part of the Wellbeing Economy Governments initiative, which places citizen well-being at the heart of public policy (Layard & De Neve, 2023). These governments have found that incorporating SWB metrics helps target those areas of life most responsible for total misery, such as mental health, loneliness, or insecure work. Layard & De Neve (2023) emphasize that SWB measures make it easier to identify not only who benefits from a policy, but also who loses out, and offering a clearer picture of distributive justice and equity. Moreover, well-being analysis allows for a novel kind of cost-benefit assessment, one that avoids the distortions of monetization by directly measuring policy impacts in terms of *well-being* (HM Treasury, 2021a, 2021b). For example, air pollution might be evaluated not just by its economic cost but by its impact on life satisfaction, which can then be converted into equivalent monetary compensation via willingness-to-accept models.

Policies aimed at increasing SWB can have wide-ranging secondary benefits. Research shows that happier individuals are healthier, more productive, more socially engaged, and more likely to volunteer (De Neve et al., 2013). Thus, improving well-being is not just an ethical goal, it is also an economically and socially rational strategy in an indirect way (HM Treasury, 2021a). Furthermore, there is strong evidence that subjective well-being influences political behaviour. Ward (2020) found that citizens with higher life satisfaction are significantly more likely to support incumbent governments. Conversely, lower well-being is associated with protest inclination and heightened political interest, particularly among youth (Lorenzini, 2015; Layard & De Neve, 2023). In this sense, well-being functions as an early-warning indicator of political instability, as illustrated during the Arab Spring, where declines in life satisfaction (not in income) predicted unrest (Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2019).

“Think about, when there are elections, I guess also national policymakers would be quite interesting in understanding what the level of subjective well-being of the national population, what are the domains that make people more satisfied, what are the domains that people make less satisfied”

Expert interview, former OECD economist

While the case for incorporating SWB into policy is compelling, it is not without caveats. Several scholars warn against positioning SWB as the supreme policy objective. Taylor (2018) argues that governments face normative and practical limits in promoting well-being, especially given the pluralism of values in liberal societies. Similarly, Graham & MacLennan (2020) advise against creating ministries devoted solely to well-being, fearing bureaucratic isolation and mission creep. Others point to cultural blind spots: the pursuit of happiness can inadvertently reinforce dominant norms that marginalize women, LGBTQ+ people, and racial

minorities (Ahmed, 2010). Bache & Scott (2018) note that EU and OECD policy documents often treat well-being as culture-neutral, neglecting the specific ways that marginalized groups experience and define happiness. Nonetheless, such critiques need not invalidate the well-being approach. Rather, they emphasize the importance of contextual sensitivity, pluralism, and institutional humility. As Sen (1980) argued, policies should focus not on prescribing a single model of the good life, but on expanding people’s capabilities to choose for themselves. This principle is echoed in Musikanski and colleagues. (2019), who advocate for governance structures that empower individuals rather than dictate their happiness.

Incorporating subjective well-being into policymaking does not mean replacing economic indicators or overriding democratic processes. Instead, it offers a richer, more humane lens through which to assess the effectiveness and fairness of policy. When used thoughtfully, SWB measures can help governments allocate resources more efficiently, address social injustices more effectively, and foster a political culture that values human flourishing alongside material success. As Helliwell (2018) succinctly put it, “*bringing happiness into policymaking fundamentally improves decision-making*”. In a time of growing complexity and social fragmentation, a policy paradigm that prioritizes well-being may prove not only more compassionate, but more resilient.

Identifying vulnerable and miserable groups

It is important to note that while SWB metrics alone do not provide solutions to social challenges, they serve as powerful diagnostic tools. They help illuminate the diverse factors (e.g., health status, social relationships, or workplace conditions) that shape individual and group well-being, and they reveal the varying importance of these factors across different subpopulations. One of the key advantages of policies grounded in subjective well-being is their ability to identify and support the most vulnerable segments of the population. In contrast to traditional economic models that rely on aggregate indicators, well-being-centred approaches are inherently people-focused, emphasizing individual experiences and perceptions (Durand & Exton, 2019). This shift in focus makes it possible to detect deprived or marginalized groups who may otherwise remain invisible within GDP growth or income averages (Exton & Shinwell, 2018). According to Taylor (2018), if there is limited potential to improve overall population well-being, then policies should be specifically targeted at disadvantaged groups to mitigate the negative factors affecting their lives. This approach is not only more equitable but also more efficient in terms of impact. The principle of diminishing returns suggests that societal well-being can be most effectively improved by focusing efforts on those in the worst circumstances, as the relative gains in well-being are greater for these individuals than for those already doing well (Tofallis, 2020). This logic aligns with the idea of a “not bad society” (O’Donnell, 2013), where the primary role of government is not necessarily to create maximum

happiness, but rather to alleviate misery (Diener et al., 2009). Furthermore, the application of well-being indicators allows not only for a snapshot of current conditions but also for tracking changes over time. Policymakers can assess whether the effects of specific interventions converge or diverge across population groups (Exton & Shinwell, 2018). In addition, past policies that may have contributed to present vulnerabilities can be identified, and future trends in well-being can be anticipated more accurately (Diener et al., 2009). Subjective well-being data also enable the detection of regional disparities, as differences in well-being between local areas become apparent (Hicks et al., 2013). These spatial inequalities often remain hidden when relying solely on macroeconomic indicators, despite being crucial to the success of local policy interventions.

In sum, subjective well-being-based policies offer a valuable opportunity to refocus policy attention on those most in need, while also providing a more accurate means of evaluating policy effectiveness. This contributes to a more just and targeted policy framework: one that is responsive to social inequalities and the various factors that perpetuate or exacerbate disadvantage.

5. Policy recommendations for Austria

In recent years, the well-being of immigrants has emerged as a significant issue at the intersection of migration studies and public policy. One promising example of a well-being-based approach to migration policy is found in New Zealand, where happiness metrics have been applied to evaluate integration efforts (Fry & Wilson, 2018). Yet, the degree to which immigrant happiness should be considered a priority by policymakers remains contentious. From a compassionate and rights-based perspective, it seems logical that immigrants, as legal equals, should be supported in their pursuit of happiness in their host countries (Hendriks, 2018). However, in practice, many policymakers are hesitant to invest in improving immigrant well-being. This reluctance is often driven by fears that native citizens will feel their needs are being deprioritized, or that more generous support for immigrants could increase migration flows deemed undesirable due to cultural, economic, or skill-level concerns (Castles, 2004).

To mitigate these tensions, policy interventions aimed at enhancing immigrant well-being are often encouraged to focus on less politically sensitive areas, such as language acquisition or access to accurate information about life in the host country (Hendriks, 2018). These measures not only improve the immediate integration experience but also reduce the potential for social friction. Moreover, raising public awareness about the societal benefits of happier, better-integrated immigrant populations could foster greater acceptance and more constructive discourse around immigration policy. The social consequences of well-being are also significant. Formerly we have highlighted that happier individuals tend to be more sociable, form better relationships, tend to miss fewer days from work, and contribute positively to their communities. In this way, immigrant happiness contributes to stronger social cohesion, increased productivity, and more sustainable integration outcomes. It also sets in motion a positive feedback loop: as immigrants become more engaged and successful, societal attitudes toward immigration improve, encouraging even more inclusive policies (Hendriks, 2018; Knabe et al., 2013). Importantly, integration is not only about what immigrants can do to adapt to host societies, but also about how those societies receive and support them. Similarly, the World Happiness Report (Helliwell et al., 2018) emphasizes that the well-being of immigrants is strongly tied to how accepting a host society is. This requires moving beyond “methodological nationalism” (Faist, 2012) the tendency to judge immigrants solely by the dominant norms of the host country, and instead incorporating subjective perspectives and lived experiences into evaluation frameworks (Paparusso, 2021).

Empirical research suggests that migrant well-being is not simply a derivative of objective improvements in living standards. In fact, there is a consistent gap between gains in material conditions and gains in subjective well-being (Hendriks, 2018). This disconnect underscores the limitations of assuming a linear relationship between economic improvement and life satisfaction, and calls for a nuanced understanding of how immigrants experience their new

environments. For example, immigrants' happiness is often more influenced by social acceptance, discrimination, and their ability to build networks than by income alone (Bartram, 2011). In one remarkable study Rodríguez-Puello (2025) and his colleagues have found that the negative effects of migration on well-being is only compensated by an EUR1164 increase in monthly income.

The happiness functions of immigrants, that is, the factors that determine their subjective well-being, differ meaningfully from those of the general population (Hendriks, 2018). This makes it crucial to avoid applying general well-being findings to migrant populations without careful adjustment. Successful integration policies must therefore be differentiated and context-sensitive. A “one size fits all” approach fails to capture the diversity of immigrant experiences and risks overlooking key sources of dissatisfaction or resilience (Musikanski et al., 2019). According to the OECD (2018), local and regional governments should also play a larger role in measuring and responding to immigrant well-being, as they are better positioned to understand those specific challenges and opportunities within their jurisdictions.

Despite these benefits, international migration often results in a temporary or even long-term decline in subjective well-being, particularly for migrants from lower-middle-income countries (Rodríguez-Puello et al., 2025). This suggests that migration decisions may sometimes be suboptimal, highlighting the need for better pre-migration information and guidance (Hendriks, 2018). Policymakers must help both prospective and current immigrants develop more accurate expectations and life strategies if they wish to foster thriving, not just surviving, migrant populations. A successful immigration policy requires an examination of the subjective well-being and happiness of immigrants (Yoshiaki, 2020).

In conclusion, subjective well-being offers a valuable lens through which to assess and improve migration policies. As Hendriks and Bartram (2016) assert, it is not only economic but also social and cultural constraints that shape immigrant happiness. Addressing these complexities with nuance and empathy will be essential for building societies in which all residents can thrive.

MIGWELL Facts

The subjective well-being disadvantage associated with unemployment is significant among Hungarians living in Austria.

The scarring effect is evident: individuals who lost their jobs in Austria during COVID still report lower life satisfaction to this day.

Policy recommendation 1

During the research, we did not encounter any reports indicating workplace discrimination, ethnic penalization, or exploitation. However, the continuous monitoring of these issues and the supervision of employers remain necessary.

Policy recommendation 2

Our analysis showed that unemployment has a long-term negative effect. However, this effect does not appear if the individual receives lower pay but is still able to keep their job. A typical example of this was the Kurzarbeit scheme during COVID, whose positive impact we confirmed within the Hungarian community that was extremely affected by the pandemic. In times of crisis, the continued application of similar policies is recommended.

Policy recommendation 3

Given the profound emotional toll of unemployment, policy responses should go beyond traditional economic measures. While financial support remains necessary, interventions that also consider psychological resilience, self-worth, and social connectedness are likely to be more effective in restoring well-being. Mental health support, retraining programs that include psychological counselling, and active labour market policies promoting meaningful employment opportunities can help counteract the long-term scars of joblessness. Paying attention to mental health problems caused by job loss or unsuccessful job searching is particularly important in the early stages of migrant life in Austria (scarring effect), as well as for transnational migrants who support their families (due to high expectations that the individual may not be able to fulfil). Hungarian civil organizations providing mentoring and psychological support are already in operation, and it would be beneficial to collaborate with them.

Policy recommendation 4

Policy should focus on the so called “trailing partners”, individuals who did not intend to migrate themselves but moved abroad due to their partner’s employment. These individuals are predominantly women and are primarily responsible for managing the household. Those migrants have pronounced integration difficulties. Their integration through employment should be encouraged, by facilitating simplified employment procedures and supporting self-employment opportunities.

“And the task of the wife or the partner will not be to advance professionally and establish her life here, but to provide a stable family background. And they are the ones who never really ‘arrive’ [in Austria]. Especially emotionally. Because traditionally, it is also the role of women to take care of the family members who stay at home. Generally, the strongest identity of the women who arrive here is their maternal identity; their professional identity is lost.”

Expert interview, psychology scholar

Policy recommendation 5

Mothers who have lost their sense of identity often struggle with mental health issues and show signs of negative affective states. Psychotherapy services should be more actively promoted within this group: in Hungarian, in environments they perceive as safe, and free from stigma or judgment.

“Very, very rarely do they [the Hungarian mothers] go to psychotherapy. They say: ‘Uh, it’s very expensive. It’s not accessible, there are long waiting lists, going home is difficult, and besides, it’s shameful, because people in Hungary look at us and say you’ve got it made, don’t complain.’ And this is a huge trap. These are taboos.”

Expert interview, psychology scholar

Literature review (Recommendations 1-5)

Unemployment is widely acknowledged as one of the most detrimental experiences to individual well-being. Beyond the immediate economic implications, losing one’s job can deliver a severe psychological blow, often diminishing self-worth and optimism. For many, unemployment signals a personal failure or perceived loss of social value, which in turn undermines self-esteem and long-term life satisfaction (Diener et al., 2009). While financial compensation and unemployment benefits may alleviate some of the material hardship, they do not fully compensate for the psychological damage caused by joblessness. As Frey and Stutzer (2002) argue, the subjective impact of unemployment reaches far beyond income loss. In fact, even reemployment may not completely erase these effects. Individuals who have experienced unemployment in the past tend to report lower life satisfaction than those who have never been unemployed, a phenomenon known as the scarring effect (Clark et al., 2021).

Importantly, the psychological burden of unemployment is not distributed evenly across labour segments. Manual workers, or blue-collar employees (where the Hungarian migrant population is overrepresented), often suffer more from the loss of employment than their white-collar counterparts. This disparity may stem from differences in job identity, workplace security, and reemployment opportunities (Paul, 2005). Moreover, not only unemployment itself but also job insecurity and the fear of potential job loss negatively affects well-being as well. Even

individuals currently in employment may experience stress and reduced satisfaction if they perceive their job as unstable (Green, 2011).

For immigrants, employment is a critical pathway to both socio-economic integration and improved subjective well-being. Yet they often face disproportionate barriers in the labour market, including higher unemployment rates, underemployment, and overqualification. These conditions not only limit immigrants' economic potential but also expose them to greater psychological and social stress. Efforts could help mitigate employment penalties, reduce ethnic discrimination, and foster a greater sense of purpose and inclusion (Paparusso, 2021).

MIGWELL Facts

25-30% overqualified, more common among women.

In cases of overqualification, satisfaction with work and income is lower, and the likelihood of stress is higher.

The proportion of those willing to accept jobs below their qualification level is increasing.

Policy recommendation 6

Establishing retraining programs for highly qualified workers would be beneficial, enabling them to find employment in fields related to (if not exactly matching) their original professions. One of our interviewees mentioned a former program in which immigrant economists were retrained to become Central and Eastern Europe experts.

Policy recommendation 7

Encouraging and motivating individuals stuck in low-skilled jobs is important. Additionally, raising awareness that with German language skills, finding employment in their own profession is now easily achievable, especially for doctors and teachers, is crucial.

"Anyone who speaks German can find a job in their own profession."

Policy-maker interview, Member of the Hungarian Ethnic Group Council

Literature review (Recommendations 6-7)

Evidence points to potential downsides of overqualification. Chen and colleagues (2010) report that overqualified migrants tend to have poorer mental health compared to other migrants. This suggests that the mismatch between qualifications and job requirements can take a psychological toll. Maynard and colleagues (2006) argue that overqualification can negatively affect well-being in multiple ways: by lowering earnings, reducing job satisfaction, and weakening emotional attachment to the workplace. Moreover, social comparison related to migrants' social status in their country of origin plays an important role in subjective well-being, especially for highly educated immigrants who struggle to transfer their skills. Calvo and Sarkisian (2015) emphasize that understanding these dynamics is essential for grasping the subjective well-being of migrants in the destination country. However, the subjective evaluation of overqualification in the workplace is not uniformly negative. Haindorfer (2020) highlights through qualitative interviews with commuters from Hungary that many migrants perceive overqualification as a meaningful temporary solution, which offers an opportunity to improve their German language skills and facilitates easier job searching later on.

MIGWELL Facts

Social exclusion is one of the most important factors influencing the subjective well-being of Hungarians living in Austria.

When it comes to satisfaction with social relationships, an urban-rural gap appears, but the urban advantage is smaller in Austria than in Hungary.

The only affective domain where the improvement is not evident is loneliness.

Policy recommendation 8

Although Hungarians do not report discrimination to the same extent as some more distant ethnic groups due to cultural closeness and historical traditions, introducing Hungarian culture and the minority community through education would be important for Austrian society.

“In intercultural projects, the main goal is primarily to introduce the local minority group to the majority society here. Because children simply receive zero information during history or other education in school about the fact that there are ethnic groups living in Austria. It’s non-existent, they know nothing about it.”

Policy-maker interview, Member of the Hungarian Ethnic Group Council

Policy recommendation 9

Promote group activities after work through “social prescribing”, supporting immigrant integration via culture and sports (which in themselves contribute to increased well-being), especially for alienated individuals living in urban settings.

“And the other thing is that those working abroad are very often lonely because they don’t have social connections. It is typical that if someone goes abroad to work, they don’t have separate after-work activities, they don’t maintain relationships with locals, and they don’t really integrate into the host society, while those left behind have their family, friends, and familiar environment here. So those working abroad have to face this as well. And precisely because they don’t have connections or activities, they are abroad only to work.”

Expert interview, political sociologist

Policy recommendation 10

Children are important cultural brokers in the successful social integration and relationship-building of their parents, whether with members of the host society or with those of the minority community. Primarily, it is their social connections that should be strengthened, the parents’ social integration will then follow.

“I always say it’s very important that they bring the children here so they can learn to read and write, but what’s even more important is that the children have Hungarian peers. It’s because of them that they’ll still be willing to attend Hungarian classes, learn Hungarian, or speak Hungarian even five years from now.”

Policy-maker interview, Vice-president of the Hungarian Ethnic Group Council

“Because when someone becomes a mother, her social network is also defined by the child for quite a while. When the children are still very young, you’re forced to stay in touch with the parents of your children’s friends, who sooner or later become friends themselves or turn into quite close acquaintances.”

Expert interview, psychology scholar

Policy recommendation 11

In the narrative interviews, it came up several times that the Hungarian community is not as cohesive as other ethnic groups, and that there is a noticeable lack of trust among its members. The root of the conflict lies in the fact that the Hungarian group is made up of several layers that are often jealous of one another. Moreover, the Austrian state supports one layer of the community, while the Hungarian government focuses on another. Strengthening the social cohesion of the Hungarian community is clearly necessary, with greater emphasis placed on civil initiatives and grassroots organizing.

“...which we also have to pay attention to, namely the fact that in Austria, there are not only Hungarian immigrants, but also the diaspora, the Hungarian diaspora, which of course is much smaller than the number of immigrants... I have to say that this is starting to become a problem, and we need to pay attention to it. So, the interaction between the Hungarian migrants and the Hungarians who have been living here earlier, that is, the Hungarians of the diaspora, and in addition the Hungarians from 1956, because the Viennese diaspora includes people who moved here in '56. So, in reality, we have three layers, and I think these three layers are slowly starting to come into conflict with each other.”

Roundtable discussion, linguist

Literature review (Recommendation 8-11)

Among the various domains that shape human well-being, social relationships are among the most powerful predictors of life satisfaction. High-quality interpersonal relationships offer emotional support, a sense of belonging, and meaning in life. As Diener and Biswas-Diener (2019, p. 148) aptly note, “If there is a single ‘secret’ to happiness, it is to be found in high quality social relationships.”

Social connections contribute to subjective well-being not only on the individual level but also collectively. Individuals tend to be happier when the broader society is characterized by strong social capital and high trust levels (Putnam, 2001). In this light, social inclusion becomes a key policy priority. The European Union, for instance, explicitly recognizes the importance of limiting social exclusion and calls on its member states to implement measures aimed at fostering inclusive communities (Atkinson & Da Voud, 2000). Despite its centrality to well-being, social connectedness is not guaranteed for all. Immigrants, in particular, often report lower levels of life satisfaction due to reduced informal networks, limited trust in others, and persistent experiences of social exclusion (Tegegne & Glanville, 2019). These social deficits compound the challenges immigrants face in navigating new labour markets and cultural contexts (Hendriks, 2018).

To counteract these effects, strengthening immigrants’ social capital is a promising policy direction. Facilitating family reunification, supporting diaspora networks, and encouraging both bonding (within-group) and bridging (cross-group) social ties can improve integration outcomes and mitigate loneliness, isolation, and depression (Paparusso, 2021). Transnational practices also deserve policy support. Maintaining emotional, cultural, and economic connections with countries of origin (e.g., through remittances, frequent communication, or visits) has been shown to enhance life satisfaction without hindering integration in the host country (Ambrosetti & Paparusso, 2021).

A growing body of research also supports the idea of social prescribing, whereby individuals suffering from isolation, stress, or poor mental health are referred by medical professionals to

community groups, volunteering opportunities, or cultural activities (Layard & De Neve, 2023; Tofallis, 2020). Its relevance is further underscored by findings that social support exhibits less pronounced diminishing marginal returns than other well-being factors, even in societies where baseline levels of social capital are already high (Tofallis, 2020). Sime and Fox (2015) underline the importance of third parties (such as children, parents, and friends) in forming friendships. These “cultural brokers” facilitate the connection between migrants and the host society. With their help, migrants may be more motivated to learn the host country’s language and find it easier to engage with the local community

Importantly, social connectedness is not merely a private concern. While personal choices and dispositions matter (Duncan, 2010), public policy plays a crucial role in shaping the conditions under which individuals can form and maintain meaningful relationships. Therefore, fostering supportive communities and reducing cultural biases and discrimination should be a central objective of integration and well-being policy (Beja, 2018). Beyond promoting opportunities for connection, policies must also target the structural and attitudinal barriers that hinder social integration. This includes combating xenophobia and fostering mutual understanding between natives and immigrants. As Layard and De Neve (2023) emphasize, societies must give at least as much evidence-based policy attention to families and community-building as they do to economic growth.

MIGWELL Facts

11% of Hungarians in Austria speak only basic level German, and the true figure may be higher. Lower proficiency is more common among men and recent migrants.

Lack of language skills are closely associated with social exclusion.

Low language proficiency also aligns with higher return intentions.

Policy recommendation 12

German language proficiency is key to the successful social and economic integration of Hungarian workers in Austria. Language education for migrants is also among the least controversial public expenditures from the perspective of the host society. It is therefore advisable to offer subsidized or low-cost German language courses, or financial support for language learners already in the sending country. This early investment increases employability, accelerates integration, and reduces the burden on host-country institutions.

„Whereas before, only those who already spoke German would come here - because that's how they got their jobs - now many people come with the mindset of “I'll find a job and then learn German.” It should really be emphasized in any forum possible that it's much more practical and cheaper to learn German in Hungary beforehand if they plan to come here, rather than starting from zero once they arrive.”

Policy-maker interview, Vice-president of the Hungarian Ethnic Group Council

„The children come to Hungarian-language courses. I have to say that 90% of the mothers do not speak German. And here they have to prepare their children for school. And the person working there as well, the teachers who work for me, two of them are employees. One of them speaks German fluently, but the other has been here for 10 years and if she has to go into a shop, she turns red. And she doesn't dare to say a single sentence. So, for me, that already excludes any form of well-being. In this country, you always have a feeling of inferiority.”

Roundtable discussion, linguist

Policy recommendation 13

Language skills as a key element of integration are much less emphasized in the case of EU migrants compared to those from third countries. EU immigrants are generally less aware of available language learning opportunities and are less encouraged to participate. This is an area where improvement is clearly needed.

„Because we have migrants, let's say, among the Arab migrants, from Syria and so on, and so on. And they are forced – but for me this is not coercion – to attend German courses, so that they somehow integrate into society, at least to a small extent. And the people coming from the European Union, Hungarians, they have no possibility for this. No one tells them, like, listen, go there, take part in a German course, which would be better for you or something like that. So, I think there should also be infrastructure provided by politics.”

Roundtable discussion, linguist

Policy recommendation 14

For immigrants, maintaining their own cultural identity while integrating into the host society leads to the most fulfilling outcomes. Preserving the mother tongue plays a crucial role in this dual process. Establishing bilingual schools, where both the host country's language and the migrants' native language are taught, can support educational success, strengthen self-esteem, and foster intercultural understanding.

„In 1994, other association leaders succeeded in achieving formal legal recognition that members of the autochthonous ethnic groups also live within the territory of Vienna. This was a huge step forward, but it meant nothing from the perspective of education, because the Act on School Education for Ethnic Minorities does not apply.”

Policy-maker interview, Vice-president of the Hungarian Ethnic Group Council

Literature review (Recommendations 12-14)

Language is a crucial tool enabling migrants to access and experience various aspects of the host society. Décieux and Murdock (2021) found a clear link between language competence and a sense of belonging. However, Berry (2006) highlights that using the host country's language in many situations can act as a stressor, causing immediate acculturative stress and tension. Similarly, Horwitz and colleagues (1986) emphasize that using the second language can evoke negative emotions, such as anxiety over making mistakes, fear of negative judgments or rejection, shame and confusion about language skills, and frustration during errors. At the same time, language competence affects migration decisions. Ette and colleagues (2016) showed that better local language skills reduce migrants' intentions to return to their home countries.

Poor knowledge of the host country's majority language is negatively associated with life satisfaction among ethnic minorities (Beier & Kroneberg, 2013). Correspondingly, Haindorfer (2020) found a positive relationship between the level of German language proficiency and the subjective well-being of Hungarian commuters to Austria. Moreover, Sand and Gruber (2018) note that older immigrants generally have fewer or different friendships and community ties compared to native peers due to language and cultural barriers. Hendriks and Birnberg (2023) found that migrants who are not fluent in the dominant language of the host country generally feel happier when communicating in their native language. They also showed that interactions with natives negatively affect momentary happiness among culturally less integrated migrants. Language schools, for instance, can offer safe environments for migrants to practice the majority language without experiencing negative momentary effects. Family members who speak the majority language well, such as spouses from the host country, can also provide supportive settings for language practice.

Policy measures, such as the EU Blue Card program, offer employment opportunities, competitive salaries, language and cultural orientation courses, and permanent residence permits for high-skilled migrants from non-EU/EEA countries. Giovanis and colleagues (2021) report that these provisions positively affect migrants' participation in cultural activities and subsequently increase their subjective well-being.

6. Policy recommendations for Hungary

Traditional migration theories have often focused on objective indicators to explain why individuals choose to emigrate. However, growing evidence suggests that subjective well-being (both the individual and the country-level one) provides a more robust and nuanced explanation of migration desires than economic indicators alone (Cai et al., 2014; Lovo, 2014). While high-SWB countries benefit from a “happiness gain” by attracting migrants, the countries of origin may suffer a “happiness drain”, a loss of their happier, more engaged, and potentially more productive citizens. This phenomenon may lead to negative social and economic consequences, especially if the most satisfied individuals choose to leave (Ivlevs, 2014).

MIGWELL Facts

Potential migrants have lower life satisfaction and optimism scores, than stayers, but they are happier on the other hand.

SWB is a causal determinant of migration intention.

Lower SWB indicates higher likelihood of moving to Austria compared to other countries.

Policy recommendation 15

Our analysis showed that there is a causal relationship between low life satisfaction and the intention to migrate. Therefore, continuous monitoring of subjective well-being becomes necessary in order to assess migration potential. Besides satisfaction with life, eudaimonic variables are better indicators of migration potential than affective ones.

“A salary in Hungary is not enough to support the family, so they constantly take on extra jobs and overtime, living in a kind of hamster wheel where they work from morning until late at night, leaving no time for the children, feeling stressed, and constantly having financial problems despite working at two jobs. They feel they cannot save money or even afford small expenses that have come up for the children, like a pair of boots for winter or glasses. These are not big things, not luxury items they cannot buy, but basic necessities. Because of this compulsion to live month to month, working a lot and being stressed, this is what sparks the idea of working abroad or migrating.”

Expert interview, political sociologist

“Emigration is nothing other than the Géza Hofi of this system, because that’s where the steam is let off, it can’t build up, it can’t turn into discontent. This too has its own dynamics, its own science.”

Policy-maker interview, politician

Literature review (Recommendation 15)

As with human capital, happiness can be seen as a valuable societal resource, and both migrant-sending and receiving countries should be mindful of its distribution. Based on the research of Ivlevs (2014) it can be stated there was U-shaped association between SWB and migration intention in Central-Eastern Europe. Both the least and the most happy individuals indicated a higher migration potential. However, research conducted in this region in recent years aligns with the international trend, which shows that individuals with lower levels of subjective well-being are more likely to express a desire to migrate internationally (Cai et al., 2014). Key factors influencing emigration desires include satisfaction with living standards, community belonging, leisure time, and environmental quality (Turulja et al., 2022). Moreover, countries with higher average levels of life satisfaction tend to be more attractive as migration destinations. Aggregated SWB measures may therefore serve as a more comprehensive reflection of a country’s desirability than traditional economic data (Lovo, 2014). This has important policy implications, suggesting that fostering subjective well-being could enhance a country’s international appeal.

MIGWELL Facts

Inequality in SWB is higher in Hungary, than among Hungarians living in Austria.

Largest inequality is found in satisfaction with income.

Policy recommendation 16

Well-being policies should primarily focus on improving the situation of the most disadvantaged and vulnerable groups, where each unit of financial investment yields significantly greater increases in well-being. Such targeted efforts would reduce substantial well-being inequalities and contribute to a healthier society overall.

“Where I think Hungarian social policy could have a role is in trying to help in hopeless situations, when someone truly goes abroad out of necessity.”

Expert interview, political sociologist

Policy recommendation 17

Our analysis has shown that, in the case of potential migrants, certain factors are associated with significantly lower life satisfaction compared to those intending to stay. Since low life satisfaction is one of the causal factors of migration potential, addressing the factors linked to this low satisfaction is of key importance. These factors are the following: deprivation and unemployment.

Policy recommendation 18

In parallel with the previous suggestion, certain factors are associated with significantly higher life satisfaction among potential migrants compared to those intending to stay. Supporting the realization of these factors would also be important in order to encourage residents to remain in Hungary. These factors are the following: meeting with friends and having a partner.

Policy recommendation 19

Based on our survey, Hungarian society is not as deeply divided on issues of immigration and emigration as political rhetoric suggests. The goal should be to foster a more constructive tone in public discourse, where emigrants are not stigmatized as traitors but recognized as individuals who can bring knowledge and financial resources back to Hungary.

“The employment of mothers abroad, especially if a minor child remains at home in Hungary, is condemned. Yes, unfortunately, it is condemned. The problem is that people do not see that these are truly forced decisions; if a mother decides to go abroad, she does so solely because of her family.”

Expert interview, political sociologist

“The task is clearly to outline a vision of a more peaceful tone and a more cohesive society.”

Policy-maker interview, politician

“And the problem is not that they leave. We actually approved of them going away for a few years, earning money, gaining knowledge. But then they should come back.”

Policy-maker interview, politician

Literature review (Recommendations 16-19)

Austin (2018, p. 49) contends that the most meaningful response to the classic philosophical question “Equality of what?” is simply: well-being. This perspective suggests that a just society is one that minimizes disparities in life satisfaction and emotional welfare, not merely one that ensures equal access to goods or opportunities. While economic indicators such as income or health status are frequently used to assess societal progress, growing evidence suggests that inequalities in subjective well-being offer a more accurate and nuanced picture of a society’s true condition (Helliwell et al., 2020). Disparities in how people experience their lives may reveal latent social tensions that objective data alone cannot capture. The broader understanding that reducing inequality is not merely a question of fairness or redistribution, it is also instrumental to enhancing overall happiness. While income equality on its own has a limited direct effect on average life satisfaction, the distribution of well-being matters. Societies with more equal distributions of subjective well-being tend to exhibit higher average levels of life satisfaction. Accordingly, Layard and De Neve (2023, p.45.) argue that “it is more important to raise the wellbeing of the least happy people than to raise by an equal amount the wellbeing of those who are already quite happy.”

Trust plays a central role in shaping both individual and collective well-being. In societies where individuals report high levels of trust toward others, subjective well-being is significantly higher (Layard & De Neve, 2023). Importantly, trust has a disproportionately positive effect on those who are economically or socially disadvantaged, making it a key equalizing force. Thus, fostering a high-trust society can not only improve average well-being but also help reduce inequalities in well-being outcomes.

To achieve such a rebalancing, policies must aim not only to equalize economic resources but also to reduce unchosen disadvantages stemming from birth or social position. As Roemer (1998) posits, inequalities that result from circumstances outside an individual’s control (country of birth for example) should be corrected, whereas inequalities arising from personal choices may be more ethically permissible. This distinction provides a framework for targeted interventions aimed at levelling the playing field without suppressing individual autonomy.

From a policy standpoint, this implies prioritizing measures that support the most vulnerable groups, for example through expanded social safety nets, mental health services, and protections against economic insecurity (Layard & De Neve, 2023). These interventions do more than alleviate hardship; they raise the well-being of those at the bottom of the distribution and, in doing so, improve the moral and emotional fabric of the society as a whole.

MIGWELL Facts

9.4% is planning to return to Hungary in the next three years.

Return reasons: Relationships, achieved goal, safety.

Returnees reported lower life satisfaction than those who planned to stay, and even lower than the average of potential migrants still living in Hungary.

Not all returnees are dissatisfied. “Target earner” group, who achieved their specific group experienced a large increase in SWB.

Policy recommendation 20

The very first step in a successful return migration policy is a thorough assessment of the well-being of Hungarians living abroad, to understand what makes them happy and what is missing from their lives.

“We deal with it, and generally will continue to deal with where Western Europe is heading, and what push-pull factors will specifically support return migration.”

Policy-maker interview, ministerial commissioner

Policy recommendation 21

The second step is addressing the inequalities previously mentioned and improving basic living conditions in Hungary, thereby making the country attractive again. Hungarian migrants in Austria, due to their active transnational lifestyle, gain personal experience of these conditions first-hand, so they do not have to rely solely on the media or Hungarian institutions abroad.

“I don’t really see the point of a policy that tries to magically lure young people back home with something, because these one-time magic gestures can’t offset the fundamentals. ... I basically think that emigration and return migration policy is a very, very secondary step, and it only makes sense to talk about it if the fundamentals are in place.”

Policy-maker interview, politician

“I think that when you, in your research, examine a number of factors that drive migration. It is an oversimplification if the political response is simply: just come home, because you are so patriotic... So, I think if we want to respect the people who left our country, then we should rather examine the factors that made them leave the country.”

Roundtable discussion, politician

Policy recommendation 22

Only after this can specific policies be developed, primarily focusing on highly skilled individuals with high added value, by targeting factors identified through understanding their specific well-being needs.

“I think it makes more sense to invest in things like this - to try to lure back scientists or professionals living and working abroad with various financial schemes. And obviously, the more they are engaged in high value-added work, the more important it is to bring them back to Hungary.”

Policy-maker interview, politician

Policy recommendation 23

The Hungarian government should aim to attract returnees not primarily through material incentives, but through “softer” factors, areas in which this group currently experiences shortages and, as a result, lower life satisfaction. These include, for example, the role of social connections and family.

“We see a way out of this through family policy. We tried to show in maybe one or two slides why it’s worth coming back home, or why Hungary might be a good place. Safety, family policy, in terms of quality of life, Hungary has many advantages. Home ownership, for example: someone living in Munich or Vienna. When will they be able to own a home with the property prices there? I think a Gastarbeiter has no chance. In Hungary, they have a chance, if they start a family, if they can access the government support available. ... What is interesting is that with return migration, the question of identity often comes up. Or differences in values. That they encounter people, values in the given country that are no longer acceptable to them.”

Policy-maker interview, ministerial commissioner

Policy recommendation 24

Children often bear the consequences of their parents’ (especially their mothers’) loss of identity. Parents also mistakenly believe in the myth that children effortlessly absorb every language and piece of new information, and that they have no difficulties integrating. In reality, the success or failure of migration often hinges on the children, as they are the ones who ultimately influence whether the family stays abroad or returns home. This is a heavy burden to place on them, and it often manifests in behavioural problems that can persist even after returning home. Families and children in this situation should receive targeted support from native-language professionals, and such services need to be actively promoted among migrant communities.

“The children become parentified. They are the ones who have to decide whether their parents stay or go back. And this is a very difficult thing for an eight- or a twelve-year-old. And this has real physical and mental health consequences.”

Roundtable discussion, psychology scholar

Literature review (Recommendations 20-24)

Permanent settlement in a new country is not a given outcome of migration. Especially for migrants from highly developed countries, migration is often seen as a temporary phenomenon. This temporary nature of migration can be advantageous for both sending and receiving countries (Van Houte & Davis, 2013). Reflecting this, destination countries frequently treat migrants as a temporary labour force and design immigration policies that favour short-term stays rather than long-term settlement (Boese & Robertson, 2017). In this context, promoting managed circular migration systems could create a “win–win–win” scenario benefiting all parties involved (Paparusso, 2021).

Life satisfaction emerges as a valuable indicator for analysing return migration behaviour. Return intentions are influenced by a complex mix of economic, social, and subjective factors related to migrants’ personal satisfaction (Mara & Landesmann, 2013). While returnees are generally not happier than individuals who never migrated (Erlinghagen, 2011), they tend to be less satisfied than migrants who remain in the host country (Ette et al., 2021). Moreover, return migrants often experience a negative relationship between income and satisfaction, a phenomenon termed by Graham and Pettinato (2002) as “frustrated achievers,” where higher income correlates with lower subjective well-being. Building on this, Sallam (2024) argues that the intention to migrate positively predicts actual return migration and that lower life satisfaction is associated with higher odds of both intending to return and actually returning. Thus, improving migrants’ subjective well-being in host countries may be a key policy tool to reduce return migration (Sallam, 2024).

The influence of life satisfaction in the home country is particularly significant for migrants with strong transnational ties. Research shows that the average life satisfaction of demographically similar stayers in the country of origin serves as a robust predictor of migrants’ return intentions, indicating that migrants tend to be well-informed about the living conditions awaiting them back home (Schiele, 2021).

Although migrants may revise their plans over time, understanding the drivers behind return intentions is crucial for anticipating future migration trends. This knowledge helps shape integration and reception policies in host countries (Paparusso, 2021). These findings carry important implications for both researchers and policymakers. While economic prosperity attracts migrants, it is ultimately the perceived quality of life that influences their decision to stay. A mismatch between high income and low subjective well-being among migrants may result in higher turnover rates. Consequently, countries of origin that find it difficult to compete

economically with host countries could consider investing directly in improving the life satisfaction of the target groups they aim to encourage to return (Schiele, 2021).

In recent years, several Hungarian governments have attempted to promote return migration. The “Gyere haza, fiatal!” program, for instance, focused solely on financial incentives, which led to social tensions and ultimately proved unsuccessful. In contrast, the “Lendület” program, primarily targeting young researchers, has achieved more promising results. The most recent initiative is the “Hazaváró” program, launched in 2023. It functions primarily as an administrative service aimed at guiding potential returnees through the maze of bureaucratic challenges and offering solutions to their problems. The program has already helped thousands of people successfully return to Hungary.

7. Policy recommendations for both countries

MIGWELL Facts

Among Hungarians living in Austria, unfavorable wealth comparisons with Austrians have a negative effect on satisfaction.

This effect is smaller among those engaged in active transnationalism.

Hungarians planning to migrate to Austria expect a greater social leap than those intending to move to other countries.

Policy recommendation 25

Although counselling to help adjust overly high expectations and prepare migrants for the difficulties ahead is already in place at Hungarian EURES offices, it is important that potential workers do not perceive this solely as a tactic by the Hungarian government to keep them at home. In reality, such guidance serves their long-term interests as well. The Austrian government could also assist in this effort, as it is not in their interest either for workers to return home disappointed and subsequently discourage other potential migrants.

„I think that the most important thing here is self-awareness. Some have it, some don't. And how much tolerance they have. ... I also see that often the problem is exaggerated expectations. For this, I usually say that over there, the fence isn't made of sausages either.”

Expert interview, EURES advisor

“We mainly focus on what kinds of traumas a person may experience, or rather, trauma is not the right word, but what kinds of pitfalls and difficulties such foreign employment may have.”

Expert interview, EURES advisor

Policy recommendation 26

Particular attention should be paid to immigrants' unfavourable comparisons with the rest of society, as these determine low life satisfaction. Supporting active engagement with their home community may offer a solution to this issue.

Literature review (Recommendations 25-26)

The expectations that immigrants hold prior to and during their migration process play a crucial role in shaping their subjective well-being. Research shows that life satisfaction among migrants increases as the disadvantage between themselves and reference groups narrows or even turns into an advantage. This relationship is particularly strong when comparing migrants' income to that of natives, suggesting that upward comparison has a stronger impact on subjective well-being than downward comparison (Stranges et al., 2021).

However, unmet expectations or shifting frames of reference over time can lead to disillusionment. As immigrants become more familiar with their host society, they may begin to assess their progress and success through the lens of local norms and standards. If their aspirations remain unfulfilled, this can result in frustration and lower levels of well-being. Hendriks (2018) suggests that slowing down or delaying this shift in reference frames could improve subjective well-being outcomes and help promote more successful integration. One promising approach suggested by Hendriks (2018) is to encourage a dual frame of reference, where migrants maintain a connection to their country of origin while adjusting to the new environment, rather than fully replacing one cultural identity with another. Such an approach can help temper overly optimistic expectations and reduce the sense of failure or disappointment that may emerge when reality falls short of hope.

Accurate and realistic information about the host country before and during the migration process can also help align expectations with likely outcomes. This could lower the number of migrants who later feel disillusioned and are unable to contribute meaningfully to their new society (Hendriks, 2018). Nevertheless, governments may hesitate to provide such information directly, fearing it could be interpreted as anti-immigration messaging. Instead, a more effective strategy could involve supporting independent research and communication that reaches migrants through trusted channels, such as diaspora communities or the popular media (Hendriks, 2018). This indirect approach may help ensure that migrants have a more grounded understanding of the opportunities and challenges that await them, ultimately supporting both individual well-being and broader integration outcomes.

MIGWELL Facts

High transnational activity: 47% provide remittances,
23% has left-behind partner or child,
33% visits home at least once a month.

Obligation related activities hurt women more.

Importance of the capability of getting help from Hungary.

Policy recommendation 27

Accurate insights into transnational practices and household structures require coordinated efforts and harmonized data collection between sending and receiving countries' statistical agencies. Without such cooperation, data gaps and inconsistencies may lead to flawed conclusions and ineffective policymaking.

“We cannot for sure give here any valid data on these on this phenomenon [transnationalism]. We know it exists. It is necessary that there is a cooperation between the Centra Statistical Office of Hungary and the Statistics Austria to find those cases. I don't know about those corporations until now.”

Expert interview, Statistik Austria

Policy recommendation 28

Certain aspects of transnational lifestyles clearly enhance migrants' life satisfaction. It is therefore recommended to identify, support, and disseminate workplace best practices that accommodate and encourage such transnational activities.

„Because some spoke very positively. Not only about life in Austria, but also about the working conditions there, the boss-subordinate relationship, and the work-life balance, for example, that they are very flexible, taking into account that someone belongs to a transnational family, and they support, for example, coming home if they know there is an event at home.”

Expert interview, political sociologist

„Because children lose a lot [due to the language difficulties], they lose their grandparents. After five years of going to school here, they won't speak Hungarian anymore, and even if they go home to visit their grandmother in the summer, they won't be able to talk about anything with her.”

Policy-maker interview, Member of the Hungarian Ethnic Group Council

Policy recommendation 29

Our project highlights that transnational practices affect men and women differently, largely due to socially constructed gender roles. Women experience a pronounced decline in subjective well-being when transnational activities involve caregiving responsibilities or obligations toward children and family in Hungary. The emotional and psychological burden of fulfilling these distant caregiving expectations can lead to increased feelings of guilt, stress, and even depressive symptoms. Targeted mental health resources such as counseling, support groups, and stress-management workshops are required, focusing on coping with distant caregiving pressures. Programs should acknowledge the dual expectations of transnational care and the socially expected maternal role, helping women to navigate these responsibilities without excessive psychological strain.

Policy recommendation 30

Most research on well-being focuses primarily on the individual. However, in the context of transnational activities, it's essential to introduce and consider the concept of family well-being as well. Only by examining the well-being of the family as a whole can we fully understand the migration experience. Neither Austrian, Hungarian, nor broader international surveys currently address family well-being, and this is something that clearly needs to change.

„ One thing, however, was completely missing from the literature at that time: this is family well-being. Which means that people are not talking about themselves, but about the family and the well-being of the family? And I find this very important. And from time to time I return to this, because many people have a very individualistic view of migration, which is true. I mean, many are very individualistic when they are in their twenties, and they want to do this. But what I've been learning more and more about global migration, from Pakistan to Hungary. Family matters. It matters in many ways. It matters in decision-making, in many things. And also, in understanding the whole story.”

Expert interview, migration scholar

Literature review (Recommendations 27-30)

Transnationalism refers to patterns of life, activities and networks that span the sending and receiving countries through the formation and maintenance of multi-layered social relations by immigrants (Basch et al., 2020). Encouragingly, transnationalism does not hinder successful integration. The integration-transnationalism theory of Carling and Pettersen (2014) draws attention to the relative strengths of integration and transnationalism in relation to each other. Transnationalism can be seen to have both a protective and a detrimental effect on the well-being of migrants (Torres, 2013). According to the transnational resource hypothesis, social support and identity resources from home increase an individual's well-being (Horn &

Fokkema, 2020) Transnational communication for examples, acts as an emotional buffer and is associated with lower stress levels (Murphy & Mahalingam, 2004). Transnational ties also help with the unfavourable social comparisons in the host country. They allow the immigrant to acquire a higher social status by comparing himself or herself to those who stayed at home (Horn & Fokkema, 2020). Based on these evidences, transnational practices should therefore be supported, not discouraged, by policymakers in both origin and destination countries (Paparusso, 2021).

However, on the negative side of transnationalism, it should be mentioned that frequent contacts can also reinforce feelings of separation and cause an identity crisis in the new country, which can lead to a decline in well-being. This is described by the transnational stress hypothesis (Horn & Fokkema, 2020): with frequent return home, family visits, intention to return and buying food from the sender country being associated with lower subjective well-being. Intense transnational ties may also have an indirect effect on subjective well-being. Indeed, they hinder (by consuming time and resources) migrants' ability to develop meaningful social ties in the host society (Baumeister & Leary, 2017).

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